

IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPMENT CENTERS IN FORMATION OF SOCIAL COMPETENCE OF PREPARATORY GROUP STUDENTS

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Abstract. *In the content of this article, the meaning of the concepts of "competency", "competence", "social competence" and the importance of developmental centers in the development of social competence of preschool children in preschool educational organizations are given.*

Keywords: *competence, competence, communication, communicative quality, science, nature, center, speech, art, game, dramatization, construction, mathematics.*

Over the last ten years, a number of developed countries, like Europe, the USA, and Russia, have been accelerating the radical reform of the higher education system in our country. In this, the main attention is paid to the formation and improvement of competence in accordance with the levels of future specialists. Today, in all parts of the educational system, especially in higher education, a completely new type of specialist is required. According to the demand of the society, the future pedagogue in a new form should develop into an active creative thinker, inquisitive, expert who independently searches for scientific information and uses it in his practical activities.

According to pedagogic scientists, it is useful to base the competence approach, which is considered as one of the main criteria, in the reformation, renewal and improvement of higher education in training specialists who meet the requirements of the time. The introduction of such a method of teaching and training in higher education requires a fundamental change in the traditional views of future specialists. In higher education, it is evident that the main focus on students' acquisition of knowledge, skills and experiences is lacking. Looking at modern pedagogy and scientific research, we notice that students pay a lot of attention to various fields and specialties, science and its methods, teaching methods, and pedagogical technologies. However, understanding their acquired knowledge, skills, qualifications and pedagogical methods, and applying them in practical activities remains one of the most urgent problems. The problem is to train future specialists studying in higher education to become competitive specialists in accordance with the requirements of the new era so that they do not have problems in applying pedagogical theoretical knowledge in their field to practical activities. To be more specific, the reason for the lack of skills of applying theoretical knowledge in practice among the teachers working today is the loss of the possibility of encountering such situations. It's no secret that many teachers and pedagogues today are burdened with outdated theoretical knowledge, and they lack the qualities of being appropriate and suitable for the fundamental changes of the times. Such complex problems of competence - being the owner of competence, being the owner of such qualities as a competent pedagogue remain the main topic of debate in today's pedagogy.

The competence approach, which has developed in the education system of European countries, has invited Russian pedagogic scientists to conduct in-depth research. As a result of the conducted scientific research, it was found that the relevance of the issue of competence is, first

of all, the formation and improvement of the professional competence of teachers and pedagogues. In fact, it was pointed out that in European countries and in Russia, scientific research work on the problems of pedagogical professional competence has been carried out for a quarter of a century, but there has been no definite end to these issues. If we want to look at the activities of the US higher pedagogical education system, the scientific works of B.D. Wolfson, T.N. Kurilova, Z.A. Molkova and others, if we want to know about the goals of the US pedagogical education, N.D. Nikandorova, V. Ya. Pili povsky, looking at the work of G.G. Agapova, O.O. Borovikova, V.S. Budenko and others on the professional pedagogical education of future teachers, and the work of V.B. Gargay, N.I. Kustinova and others about the system of professional development of US teachers, will be appropriate. We can imagine that the educational systems of Russia and the USA are enriched by the scientific works of the above-mentioned scientists. In the USA, Canada, Australia, and a number of European countries, it is noticeable that a continuous system of training of pedagogical personnel has been created, and it can be said that they are studying this problem in a specific system. [1;76-78.]

When translated into Uzbek, the word "competence" means "capable", "to be suitable". This word is derived from the Latin word "competere". "Competence" means a person's awareness of a certain field, the appropriate level of knowledge in this field. A.V. Khutorsky believes that the concepts of "competence" and "competence" can be distinguished as follows. Competence is a combination of personal qualities of a person (knowledge, skills, experience, methods of activity) and it is a qualitative and effective activity of a person in relation to things and processes in a certain area. Competence means that a person has a set of competencies that express his personal attitude to the types of activities and meet the requirements. As can be seen from the above, the issue of competence continues to be debated about its place in society.

When the concept of "competence" is analyzed from a psychological point of view, it entered the field of education as a result of psychological scientific research. From a psychological point of view, competence is "the expert's ability to behave in unconventional situations, in unexpected situations, to communicate, to take a new approach in relations with opponents, to perform ambiguous tasks, to use information full of contradictions, to consistently develop and possessing a plan of action in complex processes" means the level. From the pedagogical point of view, "competence" means the possession of knowledge, skills and competences, education, self-expression as a person, realization of one's identity, understanding of one's place in the world, knowing the purpose of living. since its goal is directed to the individual, it is the source of the qualities of mobilizing one's capabilities to the fullest, being recognized by others.

Determining the basic elements of universal competence in the field of education is one of the main problems of modern pedagogy. Regarding the issue of basic competence, there are many opinions regarding the application of the experience of world pedagogues or the determination of competence criteria based on the norms of traditional Uzbek pedagogy, and there are still many unresolved issues. But by summarizing the results of the research, it was proved that professional competence is important for the educational process. [2;5-9.]

Qualities reflected on the basis of competence are as follows:

1. Social competence is the ability to show activity in social relations, the ability to communicate with subjects in professional activities.

2. Special competence - preparation for organizing professional-pedagogical activity, rational solution of professional-pedagogical tasks, realistic assessment of the results of activity,

based on this competence, psychological, methodical, informational, creative, innovative and communicative competences are highlighted.

"Communication" comes from the Latin words "communicatio" and "communico", meaning "to connect, to communicate". The term "communication" entered science at the beginning of the 20th century. In the social sciences, communication is used to represent the field of scientific knowledge about joint action, interaction, and these processes and their outcomes. Researchers became interested in communication problems after the Second World War. As a clear example of this, it can be said that by the beginning of the 1960s, there were more than a hundred definitions of the concept of communication in the scientific literature of philosophy and sociology.

Social communication is a unique form of human interaction, in which information transfer is carried out using language and other sign systems. According to the Canadian sociologist Marshall McLuhan, the exchange of communication methods represents the stages of development in history. Accordingly, he divided the following periods of human development:

- oral communication
- written communication
- publication-communication
- multimedia communication

From the researched sources, it can be concluded that communication is aimed at establishing and ensuring interdependence between people and, first of all, it is verbal, that is, it is carried out using language (speech or text). is a specific information exchange process [4; 7-25.] .

We know that children of preschool age learn and develop their speech by playing in the centers, and their social competence skills, initiative, cooperation, and the ability to work in a group develop.

"Science and nature" center

Practical processes carried out with children in this center arouse deep interest in children and encourage them to make new inventions. This center creates the greatest opportunity for children to learn about nature and its phenomena, while forming their communication, and if this center is used effectively, it can be the basis for children to get 90 percent of their knowledge about nature here. The center is important because it arouses interest not only in children but also in pedagogues.

Through various practical processes carried out in this center, it is possible to learn the beneficial and harmful aspects of objects in the children's world and outlook. It is through this center that the children's worldview will change their relationship to them in a positive way by acquiring knowledge about where they come from and what they are used for. For example, bread coming to our table, knowing that oil comes out of a cotton seed by crushing it, seeing that there is no oil in a watermelon seed, seeing that an onion grows when it is placed in a glass of water with its root, and seeing that the seeds germinate by sprinkling them in pots. Learning is a very interesting process for children.

"Art" center

The most effective center in the development of preschool children's speech is the art center. This center is a product of raising children's mood, supporting the child's creative abilities and, as a result, educating future watchmakers. As we know, not everyone has the same talent for painting, sculpture, painting, pottery, carpentry and other types of art. Therefore, less children can

attend and pay attention to this center. However, if the necessary equipment is fully installed in the center, if the technologies of making and drawing are taught in the morning and evening hours, the work of the center will develop and the reach of children will expand. By working in this center, the child's fine motor skills develop. The development of fine motor skills leads to the development of the child's speech and, as a result, the expansion of their worldview. The next center is the center of role-playing games and dramatization.

“Plot – role-playing games and dramatization” center

This next center, which is one of the centers that can lead to the expansion of the communication space in children, is a very convenient environment for the manifestation of children's talents, for them to show their talents and skills. We can easily call this center the center that forms the "I" of the child. All the equipment in the center is the equipment found in the children's life, and during the game, the child learns to use them, and has the opportunity to get acquainted with the professions. The games reflect the mutual relations of family members, and through them, moral education and, at the same time, lead to the expansion of their friendship. (and for the educator, learning the environment in the family) creates an opportunity.

In the "Language and speech" center. Through this center, the most necessary psychological features in a child's life, from intuition to speech, are developed, which is the basis of children's communicative ability. In this center, children acquire reading and writing skills and begin to recognize sounds. But by flipping through the book, he pretends to be reading and says something. For example, we can cite familiar tales, memorized poems, conversations with friends. If we place the center a little further away from the noise, it will not be without benefits. Because when we communicate with a book, when we talk with our friends, we need silence. If our center is located in a noisy place, children will quickly get distracted and try to move from their chosen center to another center. The center should be very rich compared to other centers, because the more equipment there is in this center, the more the child will see them, talk about them, and communicate with his friends, the vocabulary will increase, his speech and world will develop.

In conclusion, it should be said that the importance of centers in preschool educational organizations is very important in the formation of social competence of preschool children. We offer the following recommendations for further enrichment and improvement of the topic.

- Studying literature and scientific journals on the subject;
- Enrichment of existing centers in pre-school educational organizations;
- To provide future educators with knowledge and skills related to the subject.
- To study the practical significance of the topic.

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